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THE INFLUENCE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE ON PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of physical culture and sports on personality development. It identifies the qualities, skills, and personal traits that are formed in an individual during the process of engaging in sports activities. Additionally, the article examines the influence of physical culture and sports on the spiritual, physical, and intellectual spheres of human life.

Key words: physical culture, sports, personality, skills, abilities, spiritual sphere, personal qualities.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada jismoniy madaniyat va sportning shaxs rivojlanishiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Sport bilan shug'ullanish jarayonida insonda shakllanadigan fazilatlar, ko'nikmalar va shaxsiy xususiyatlar aniqlanadi. Shuningdek, jismoniy madaniyat va sportning inson hayotining ma'naviy, jismoniy va intellektual sohalariga ko'rsatadigan ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy madaniyat, sport, shaxs, ko'nikmalar, qobiliyatlar, ma'naviy soha, shaxsiy fazilatlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается влияние физической культуры и спорта на развитие личности. Выявлены качества и характеристики, формирующиеся у человека в процессе занятий спортом. Также анализируется воздействие физической культуры и спорта на духовную, физическую и интеллектуальную сферы жизни человека.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, спорт, личность, навыки, способности, духовная сфера, личные качества.

INTRODUCTION

Physical education is an irreplaceable source of energy, the receipt of which provides a person with many positive benefits. In modern society, physical education and sports are highly relevant, serving as fundamental principles for ensuring and maintaining the health of the entire population. At present, sports should be integrated into a person's daily life, as there is a noticeable decline in public health levels. Today, physical education holds significant social influence and importance, playing a decisive role in the formation and development of personality. It accompanies a person through all stages of life.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sport occupies one of the main places in the life of a person. Without it, existence is simply impossible. Thanks to this, we have the opportunity to acquire and improve many skills throughout life. Physical education and sports are able to influence the development of physical data and personal qualities of a person, as well as his health. Sport is becoming more and more popular every year, bringing the physical fitness of the population to a new level. This leaves an imprint on the physical, mental, and moral state of a person. Undoubtedly, the popularization of physical culture has a beneficial effect on all areas of human life. It is impossible to limit the influence of sport to any specific moments, since it is capable of covering all manifestations in general with its influence.

Physical culture is a complex mechanism of interaction of many factors with each other, the result of which will be a morally and physically healthy person. This is the so-called ideal to which every person should strive. Sport is a key moment in the life of almost every modern person, positively influencing his physical and spiritual health and thus the results of his activities. In order to reveal and develop physical and spiritual strength in oneself, a person must have a strong desire to reach the pinnacle of physical fitness. The development of the

spiritual sphere of human life occurs due to the development of physical abilities. The personality undergoes enormous changes in terms of cultural values, principles, outlook on life, and moral principles.

Physical culture is highly valued as an internal source of personality formation. It is a person's companion to self-improvement. It should be noted that thanks to sports, a person receives the best and most valuable knowledge, applying it through experience. A person, playing sports, can acquire useful skills, without which it is impossible to develop personal qualities that successfully influence his life. With their help, a person develops character, a solid link that helps to overcome difficulties in life.

Thanks to physical activity, a person overcomes many obstacles; he develops a desire to achieve a better result, which means that the motivation to "conquer the peaks" will be stronger. Individuals who possess such qualities will have more success in their endeavors, thereby making their lives more productive. Sport helps a person to strengthen and maintain their health, is a kind of sphere of communication and social activity, helps to develop physical fitness, and also becomes a form of organizing and spending leisure time. Physical culture also determines the position in society, helps in choosing a career, and plays an important role in determining the structure of value orientations.

The result of sports can be incredibly large and effective, sometimes unknown to the person him/herself. Such a multifaceted use of sports and physical culture proves their indispensability and mandatory presence in everyday life. Sports have a strong influence on the spiritual sphere of a person's life. Under the influence of sports, a person develops a worldview, views on life, the world around him/her, his/her attitude to him/herself, his/her body and health change, thoughts are put in order, and a person is in harmony with him/herself. New goals appear, an incentive for a life filled with physical activity, and a person is charged with only positive emotions. He/she develops a desire to create and develop.

Thus, a person undergoes enormous transformations thanks to physical culture, which helps him in many other activities. It helps to understand the beauty of the human body and the spiritual beauty of the inner world. To develop the physical qualities necessary for a person, to improve coordination and teach movement, sports events are used as one of the main tools of influence. In the process of playing sports, a person acquires many useful qualities: he improves his ability to control himself and control his emotions, develops speed and correct orientation in various difficult situations, his will becomes tempered, his character is formed, timely decisions are made, and the ability to consciously take risks. Agility, endurance, strength – all this is given to a person by sports, helping to conquer the peaks. It is the desire to win that distinguishes a sports person from an ordinary one. Working for results is what is truly important for an athlete; it is necessary to give it your all, fully devoting yourself to the task in order to get a decent result and a good return.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sport gives impetus to the release of internal energy and helps a person become more active. It enables individuals to overcome their fears, push beyond their limitations, and step out of their comfort zones. It is enough for a person to embrace sport in their life for it to transform dramatically for the better, which proves the inadmissibility of a life without sport. Sport helps individuals eliminate bad habits, thereby preserving their health. It reveals one's character and hidden talents and fosters perseverance in challenging situations. An athlete trains with teammates, competes with rivals, and inevitably gains experience in human interaction – learning to understand others and offer help and support. All these qualities are essential for an individual as a member of a group in which they spend most of their life. This means that these skills are crucial for a successful communication process. Above all, the desire to change one's life, learn new things, and gain self-awareness is necessary. Without a genuine aspiration to reach the "ideal," it is impossible to improve existing skills and personal qualities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Thus, a person must constantly maintain a stimulus for progressive activity. Discovering and developing hidden potential within oneself is one of the primary goals of physical culture. In addition, the baggage of personal qualities is enriched with fearlessness, strength, speed, resilience in difficult situations, and the ability to appreciate the success of others—qualities that sport instills in a person. Through sports, a person learns to understand their body, keeps up with the times, and does not fear change. They strive for perfection and apply in practice the skills and abilities acquired through sport and physical education.

The goal of sport in forming a "newly created person" who harmoniously combines spiritual richness, moral purity, and physical integrity is profound. In a sense, sport helps each individual achieve their personal ideal. However, how perfect the acquired skills and qualities become depends on one's dedication and the desire to reach new heights. Sport thus becomes the driving force behind future success—an essential element in achieving personal excellence.

In addition, thanks to physical culture, a person's mental abilities are also enhanced. This improvement comes through the inventive mastery of technique and tactics, the ability to control emotions, and the capacity to make quick and effective decisions. A creative approach to problem-solving, the ability to think unconventionally, and occasionally make unexpected decisions are all byproducts of physical culture. This awareness often occurs at a subconscious level and later manifests in conscious actions, as it is stored in the mind over time.

It should be noted that sport not only helps acquire new skills and personal qualities but also improves and strengthens them. Physical culture activates hidden mental and physical capabilities and serves as a powerful motivator, helping individuals excel in various areas of life.

Sport is considered a vital process in the life of every person, regardless of age, background, or social status. Its enormous contribution to personal development is undeniable, as physical activity is essential for achieving many goals—goals that would be unattainable without the qualities cultivated through sports. Simply recognizing the importance of physical culture already sets a person on a path to self-improvement. The process itself allows individuals to develop numerous skills, abilities, and personal traits.

The significance of sport is immeasurable in its contribution to shaping individuals as well-rounded personalities. Due to its comprehensive impact on human development, sport holds great value not only for individuals but also for society as a whole. It cannot be removed from human life, as sport is a vital companion in the journey of progress—and without progress, as we know, no development is possible. Physical culture performs many social functions, influences the spiritual dimension of life, and plays a vital role in addressing issues of general and physical development. As such, it represents the integrated operation of a highly complex system.

CONCLUSION

The multifaceted nature of physical culture proves its indispensability in the life of every person. While it is impossible to list all the advantages of physical culture, it is enough to understand its significance personally, as its scope of impact is incredibly vast – just like the wealth of useful knowledge and skills it imparts. Sports activities offer the opportunity for a happy and long life, which is especially important in today's world. They help shape a competitive and goal-oriented individual with an active life stance.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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